

THETIDA – Living Labs for inclusive and innovative climate risk monitoring of cultural heritage

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Abstract

The THETIDA Horizon Europe project addresses the pressing need to protect coastal and underwater cultural heritage from the threats of climate change. It aims to develop and validate an integrated risk assessment and protection system through participatory processes. This paper delves into the transformative potential of Living Labs that serve as multi-stakeholder platforms to engage stakeholders and citizens in data collection and decision-making processes while placing sociocultural values in the core of risk monitoring. The THETIDA Living Lab (LL) methodology is being implemented in seven pilot sites across diverse European climates, revealing challenges in stakeholder engagement and the testing of a crowdsourcing mobile application. The study emphasizes the importance of inclusive decision-making and adaptation strategies, facilitated by a toolkit of tested methods adaptable to local contexts. Through training workshops and stakeholder feedback derived during the LL dialogues, this research contributes to understanding climate impacts on heritage and informs inclusive and sustainable multi-hazard and risk monitoring practices.

Key words

Climate change, risk monitoring, coastal heritage, underwater heritage, Living Lab, crowdsourcing

Outline

Climate change can pose serious threats to people's livelihoods, connected communities, and cultural heritage. Heritage embodies tangible (i.e., historic sites, cities, and landscapes) and intangible (i.e., cultural practices, traditions, and local knowledge) assets to which communities attach value and meaning to, and that are vulnerable to the impacts of climate change (1). Stakeholder and citizen engagement in multi-hazard and risk monitoring, preparedness, and management efforts is essential for identifying and mitigating such threats, as well as fostering inclusive and sustainable adaptation measures to protect and preserve heritage sites (2, 3).

The THETIDA Horizon Europe project aims to develop, test and validate an integrated multiple heritage risk assessment and protection system for underwater and coastal heritage sites across Europe with evidence-based monitoring frameworks, innovative tools and through participatory and crowdsourcing processes (4). This research aims to harness the full potential of Living Labs that function as multi-stakeholder platforms bringing together scientists, citizens and other relevant stakeholders in co-design and co-creation processes to engage them in data collection through crowdsourcing and to include their diverse views, reflections and priorities concerning heritage for multi-hazard and risk monitoring.

This paper presents the preliminary results of developing and testing the THETIDA Living Lab (LL) methodology, which has been implemented in seven demonstration sites across distinct European climate zones. The LL dialogues aim at assessing the values and impacts posed to the sites, as well as future scenario making and building roadmaps for inclusive and innovative multi-hazard and climate risk monitoring. A LL toolkit has been developed that compiles different sets of tested methods adaptable to local contexts that have been tested and validated in the demonstration sites. For instance, site excursions and talk shows have been employed in the coastal landscapes of the Markermeer area in the Netherlands that brought together local authorities, experts, and residents together to co-create future scenarios regarding the reinforcement of the existing dikes, the water management systems. Additionally, a novel crowdsourcing tool, an immersive mobile application that exploits Augmented Reality (AR) technology, has also been co-designed, and tested during some LL dialogues (5). For example, the AR visual demonstrating how the Svalbard coal cableway station will be immersed in water due to rapid coastal erosion and sea level rise contributes to raising awareness on this remote heritage site and facilitates discussions concerning its risk monitoring and protection.

LIVING LABS FRONTIERS

Driving systemic change through Soci(et)al Engagement,
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Results highlight diverse understandings of climate impacts, challenges and needs to be addressed. Insights and feedback are discussed in terms of strengths and weaknesses that are unique to the site, as well as the LL methods and tools employed. Such exercises are increasingly needed to customize participatory methods adapted to fit integrated multiple hazard assessment tools and strengthen sustainable and inclusive pathways for cultural heritage management (6). Overall, these processes will contribute to better understanding of the complexity of climate impacts on heritage and inform inclusive and sustainable multi-hazard and risk monitoring practices.

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